
Checklist to the Quality Assessment Process

Experiment

1. The study presents the object of study (presents what is studied? products, processes, resources, models, metrics, or theories)
 2. Does the study present the objective (intent) of the study?
 3. The study makes clear the focus on quality (which effect is studied? examples: effectiveness, cost, reliability)
 4. Has the hypothesis formulation study (null and alternative hypothesis) been performed?
 5. Are the independent and dependent variables presented clearly?
 6. Are the study hypothesis tests applied?
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Survey

1. Does the study clearly define the objectives?
 2. Does the study specify the population in terms of sources, inclusion/exclusion criteria, etc.?
 3. Does the study specify the sample (the method used: probabilistic or non-probabilistic)?
 4. Does the study report a response rate?
 5. Does the study provide a questionnaire?
 6. Does the study assess its reliability (calculate a measure of error and other threats to validity)?
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Case Study

1. Is the purpose of the article clear? Do the authors make clear what they want to achieve?
 2. Is the case study in question clearly presented?
 3. Does the study present research questions?
 4. Did the study present a theoretical basis?
 5. Does the study inform which data collection techniques are being used?
 6. Is the case study protocol defined?
 7. Does the study present the definition of the data analysis process?
 8. Does the study clarify the validity of the study by denoting the extent to which the results are true and not influenced by the subjective point of view of the researchers?
 9. Does the study present clear conclusions from the analysis?
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